

FUNCTIONAL PEARL

The cost of everything

A lightweight approach to formal algorithmic complexity

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Abstract

Proof assistants are typically used to verify a program’s correctness; reasoning about performance appears to be less straightforward. This paper explores a lightweight technique for reasoning about the algorithmic complexity of purely functional data structures and algorithms: defining a cost function by induction on a program’s graph.

1 Introduction

A LISP programmer knows the value of everything, but the cost of nothing.

— Alan Perlis, *Epigrams in Programming* (1982)

Modern proof assistants are highly effective tools for reasoning about purely functional programs. While there is a large body of work proving functional correctness of data structures and algorithms (see for instance, [Appel 2026](#)), this paper ploughs a different furrow: exploring how to reason about algorithmic complexity.

This paper aims to dispel the misconception that the *only* properties proof assistants can reason about is the *extensional* behaviour of functions, i.e., the output value computed for a given input. Although the development we present is in Agda, the same ideas can be readily ported to any other proof assistant using dependent types, including Idris, Lean or Rocq. As it turns out, these *dependent types* will be a key ingredient in our analyses of both worst case and amortized complexity.

2 Functions and relations

Q: Can proof assistants reason about complexity of programs?

A: Complexity theory is just math. And all math can be formalized.

— an exchange on the Proof Assistants StackExchange forum (2023)

To illustrate the key ideas, we revisit a classical example of functional programming: list reversal. The ‘slow’ algorithm repeatedly calls the append function on lists:

slow-reverse : List A → List A

slow-reverse [] = []

slow-reverse (x :: xs) = *slow-reverse* xs + [x]

The ‘fast’ algorithm for list reversal uses an accumulating parameter instead:

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52 $reverse\text{-}acc : (xs\ acc : List\ A) \rightarrow List\ A$
 53 $reverse\text{-}acc []\ acc = acc$
 54 $reverse\text{-}acc (x :: xs)\ acc = reverse\text{-}acc\ xs\ (x :: acc)$
 55
 56 $fast\text{-}reverse : List\ A \rightarrow List\ A$
 57 $fast\text{-}reverse\ xs = reverse\text{-}acc\ xs\ []$

58 A simple inductive argument shows that these two algorithms produce the same result. The
 59 key property relating these two definitions reads as follows:
 60

61 $reverse\text{-}correct : (xs\ ys : List\ A) \rightarrow reverse\text{-}acc\ xs\ ys \equiv slow\text{-}reverse\ xs\ +\ ys$

62 Yet we have no way to argue that one algorithm is faster than the other. In fact, if the ambient
 63 type theory supports *function extensionality*, both these functions are *equal*: after all, they
 64 produce the same output for every input list.
 65

66 What to do? Even in an intensional type theory, there is no way to observe a function's
 67 implementation. At this point, we evoke the old LISP programmer's maxim: *code is data*.
 68 The key idea is to make the definition of a function explicit by reifying the *graph* of the
 69 function as an inductively defined *relation*. In general, the graph of a function $f : A \rightarrow B$ is
 70 a relation $R : A \rightarrow B \rightarrow Set$, such that $R\ x\ (f\ x)$ holds. In the case of the *reverseAcc* function,
 71 this corresponds to the following data type:
 72

73 **data** *ReverseAcc* : $List\ A \rightarrow List\ A \rightarrow List\ A \rightarrow Set$ **where**
 74 **base** : $ReverseAcc\ []\ ys\ ys$
 75 **step** : $ReverseAcc\ xs\ (x :: ys)\ zs \rightarrow ReverseAcc\ (x :: xs)\ ys\ zs$
 76

77 You may want to think of this as a data type describing the *call graph* of the *reverse-acc*
 78 function; or alternatively, a Prolog program for reversing one list onto another. Such relations
 79 provide an *intensional* inductive description of the function's behaviour. It is straightforward
 80 to prove that this definition is sound and complete with respect to the function's definition:
 81

82 $Reverse\text{-}acc\text{-}sound : ReverseAcc\ xs\ acc\ ys \rightarrow reverse\text{-}acc\ xs\ acc \equiv ys$
 83 $Reverse\text{-}acc\text{-}complete : reverse\text{-}acc\ xs\ acc \equiv ys \rightarrow ReverseAcc\ xs\ acc\ ys$

84 But crucially, reifying the definition of the function in this fashion lets us count the number of
 85 (recursive) function calls and relate this to the size of its inputs. To do so, we define a simple
 86 *cost function*, a function that counts the size of the call graph of our reversal function:
 87

88 $cost\text{-}reverse\text{-}acc : ReverseAcc\ xs\ ys\ zs \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$
 89 $cost\text{-}reverse\text{-}acc\ base = 1$
 90 $cost\text{-}reverse\text{-}acc\ (step\ r) = 1 + cost\text{-}reverse\text{-}acc\ r$
 91

92 We would expect that the accumulating reverse function takes a number of steps linear in
 93 the size of its first argument. With these definitions, however, we make this more precise by
 94 *proving* that $reverse\text{-}acc\ xs\ ys$ requires one recursive call for each element of xs and one final
 95 step in the base case, for *any* call to *reverse-acc*:
 96

97 $(rev : ReverseAcc\ xs\ ys\ zs) \rightarrow cost\text{-}reverse\text{-}acc\ rev \equiv 1 + length\ xs$
 98

99 The proof uses straightforward induction on the graph of *reverse-acc*. In this fashion,
 100 reasoning about the complexity of a function definition is no harder than proving its functional
 101 correctness.
 102

2.1 Size and Ordnung

Algorithmic complexity relates size of inputs to the number of steps necessary to produce the output. To measure things systematically, we introduce some overloaded notation. Typically, we are interested in measuring the ‘size’ of our inputs. We introduce a record, *Size*, with a single field:

record *Size* (*A* : *Set*) : *Set* **where**
field

$|_| : A \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$

For example, we typically consider the size of a list to be its length. Now this notion of *Size* only works for types in *Set*. The graph of a function $f : A \rightarrow B$, however, will have type $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow \text{Set}$. We introduce a separate notion of size for indexed families of types:

record *Size* (*P* : $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow \text{Set}$) : *Set* **where**
field

$|_|_2 : \forall \{x : A\} \{y : B\} \rightarrow P \ x \ y \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$

Similar definitions exist for relations on more than two arguments. In the remainder of this paper, we will omit the subscripts, as these can readily be inferred.

Typically, we are not interested in the exact number of steps required, but rather want an upper bound. We introduce a (simplified) version of the typical ‘big O’ notation:

$_ \in O _ : \{ \{ \text{Size } A \} \} \rightarrow (G : A \rightarrow B \rightarrow \text{Set}) \rightarrow \{ \{ \text{Size } G \} \} \rightarrow (\mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{Set}$
 $G \in O f = \exists [c_0] \ \exists [c] \ (g : G \ x \ y) \rightarrow |x| \equiv n \rightarrow |g| \leq c_0 + c * f(n)$

We say that the relation G is in the complexity class of f when we can find constants c_0 and c , such that the cost of the graph $G \ x \ y$ is less than $c_0 + c * f(n)$, for any input x of size n . Agda’s *instance arguments* (Devriese and Piessens 2011) will search for the necessary *Size* record, when needed. This simplified definition will serve our purposes for this paper, but a much more careful treatment of asymptotic complexity in type theory can be found in Guéneau’s PhD thesis (2019).

Using this notation, we prove the accumulating reversal function is linear in its first argument, independent of the accumulating argument:

$\forall (acc : \text{List } A) \rightarrow (\lambda \ xs \rightarrow \text{ReverseAcc } \ xs \ acc) \in O (\lambda \ n \rightarrow n)$

2.2 Quadratic complexity: slow-reverse is slow

What about our slow reversal function? Can we also prove that it is quadratic? To do so, we reify the *slow-reverse* function, together with the append function it calls, by defining the graphs of both functions:

data *Append* : $\text{List } A \rightarrow \text{List } A \rightarrow \text{List } A \rightarrow \text{Set}$ **where**

base : *Append* [] *ys* *ys*

step : *Append* *xs* *ys* *zs* \rightarrow *Append* (*x* :: *xs*) *ys* (*x* :: *zs*)

data *Slow-reverse* : $\text{List } A \rightarrow \text{List } A \rightarrow \text{Set}$ **where**

base : *Slow-reverse* [] []

step : *Slow-reverse* *xs* *ys* \rightarrow *Append* *ys* [*x*] *zs* \rightarrow *Slow-reverse* (*x* :: *xs*) *zs*

154 Next, we define the obvious *cost* functions. Since *slow-reverse* calls *append*, we add the
 155 associated cost to that of the recursive call:

156
 157 $append-cost : Append\ xs\ ys\ zs \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$
 158 $slow-reverse-cost : Slow-reverse\ xs\ ys \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$
 159 $slow-reverse-cost\ base = 1$
 160 $slow-reverse-cost\ (step\ rev\ app) = 1 + slow-reverse-cost\ rev + append-cost\ app$

162 Unsurprisingly, we show that the *slow-reverse* function takes a quadratic number of steps:
 163

164
 165 $Slow-reverse \in O(\lambda n \rightarrow n * n)$
 166

167 The proof proceeds by induction on the graph of the *slow-reverse* function. The proof requires
 168 a few algebraic properties of addition and multiplication, but is otherwise straightforward.
 169

170 2.3 Counting other costs: insertion sort

171 Next consider insertion sort. The *insert* function inserts a new element into a sorted list:
 172

173
 174 $insert : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow List\ \mathbb{N} \rightarrow List\ \mathbb{N}$
 175 $insert\ y\ [] = [y]$
 176 $insert\ y\ (x : xs) = \text{if } y \leq^b x \text{ then } y : x : xs \text{ else } x : insert\ y\ xs$
 177

178 As this function has two cases when the input list is non-empty, there are two constructors in
 179 the corresponding graph.
 180

181 **data** $Insert\ (y : \mathbb{N}) : List\ \mathbb{N} \rightarrow List\ \mathbb{N} \rightarrow Set$ **where**
 182 $base : Insert\ y\ []\ [y]$
 183 $stop : y \leq x \rightarrow Insert\ y\ (x : xs)\ (y : x : xs)$
 184 $step : y > x \rightarrow Insert\ y\ xs\ zs \rightarrow Insert\ y\ (x : xs)\ (x : zs)$
 185

186 One advantage of working with function graphs directly is that we have the flexibility to
 187 define our own cost function. In particular, the analysis of a sorting algorithms typically only
 188 counts the number of comparisons:
 189

190
 191 $cost-insert : Insert\ y\ xs\ zs \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$
 192 $cost-insert\ base = 0$
 193 $cost-insert\ (stop\ x \leq y) = 1$
 194 $cost-insert\ (step\ y > x\ rec) = 1 + cost-insert\ rec$
 195

196 With these definitions in place, it is easy to prove that the *insert* function takes makes no
 197 more comparisons than the length of its input:
 198

199
 200 $(y : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow Insert\ y \in O(\lambda n \rightarrow n)$
 201

202 As a result, repeatedly calling *insert* leads to a sorting function that requires at most a
 203 quadratic number of comparisons.
 204

2.4 Intermezzo: limitations and caveats

We want to reflect briefly on the general approach. Firstly, the function’s graph and the associated cost are a crucial part of the problem specification. It is all too easy to provide ‘incorrect’ definitions. For example, there is nothing stopping us from defining a constant cost function:

```
slow-reverse-cost-wrong : Slow-reverse xs ys → ℕ
slow-reverse-cost-wrong _ = 1
```

There may be situations where such cost functions *are* desirable, as the insertion sort example above illustrates. Similarly, comparing Peano natural numbers for equality in Agda is not a constant time operation – even though we typically assume this operation to be constant time for fixed width machine integers. Having a certain degree of flexibility in the definition of cost functions is a good thing.

The graph of a function also forms part of our specification. To illustrate this point, consider the following ‘graph’ of our *slow-reverse* function:

```
data Slow-reverse-wrong : List A → List A → Set where
  wrong : Slow-reverse-wrong xs (slow-reverse xs)
```

The data type, while it also describes the graph of *slow-reverse*, is not very useful. Crucially, we expect the graphs to follow the same recursive structure as the functions they represent. Provided the type indices are built from constructors and variables, this will be the case.

How do we know these cost functions are somehow related to a program’s execution time? *Cost models* provide this missing link, relating cost functions to dynamic semantics. Fortunately, there are decades of research on this topic (Danner et al. 2015; Gurr 1990; Le Métayer 1988; Rosendahl 1989; Sands 1995; Shultis 1984; Van Stone 2003; Wegbreit 1975). Assuming a strict evaluation order, counting function calls – and thereby the size of the graph of a function – suffices (Sands 1990). The syntactic restriction on function graphs, requiring all type indices in the function’s graph to be constructors or variables, ensures that we account for all costs of any intermediate results.

3 Amortized cost and batched queues

All our analyses so far establish upper bounds on the *worst case* time complexity of our functions. In this section we explore a classic *amortized* analysis of a queue implementation using two lists. The code in Figure 1 is a variation of the batched queues from Okasaki’s classic textbook (1998). Each queue consists of two lists, the *front* and the *rear*. Elements are enqueued onto the *rear*, but removed from the *front*. Once the *front* runs out of elements, the elements in the *rear* are reversed to form the new *front*.

We enforce one invariant intrinsically: when the front of the queue is empty, so is the rear. By doing so, we know that when the *deq* operation encounters an empty *front* queue, there is no need to inspect (or reverse) the *rear*. Note that neither the *enq* nor *deq* operation is recursive. The *balance* function, however, that restores our invariant, may take non-constant time if the *rear* needs reversing.

To say anything about the cost of these queue operations, we define their graphs:

```

256 record  $Q$  ( $A : Set$ ) :  $Set$  where
257   constructor  $queue$ 
258   field
259      $front$  :  $List\ A$ 
260      $rear$   :  $List\ A$ 
261      $inv$    :  $So\ (null\ front) \rightarrow So\ (null\ rear)$ 
262
263   open  $Q$ 
264
265    $empty$  :  $Q\ A$ 
266    $empty$  =  $queue\ []\ []\ id$ 
267
268    $balance$  :  $List\ A \times List\ A \rightarrow Q\ A$ 
269    $balance\ ([],\ r)$       =  $queue\ (reverse\ r)\ []\ (const\ tt)$ 
270    $balance\ (f\ ,\ r)$     =  $queue\ f\ r\ \lambda\ ()$ 
271
272    $enq$  :  $A \rightarrow Q\ A \rightarrow Q\ A$ 
273    $enq\ x\ q$  =  $balance\ (front\ q,\ x\ ::\ rear\ q)$ 
274
275    $deq$  :  $Q\ A \rightarrow Maybe\ (A \times Q\ A)$ 
276    $deq\ (queue\ []\ r\ i)$       =  $nothing$ 
277    $deq\ (queue\ (x\ ::\ xs)\ r\ i)$  =  $just\ (x,\ balance\ (xs,\ r))$ 
278
279
280
281
282
283

```

Fig. 1. Implementing queues using two lists

```

284 data  $Balance$  :  $List\ A \times List\ A \rightarrow Q\ A \rightarrow Set$  where
285    $stop$  :  $Balance\ (x\ ::\ xs,\ ys)\ (queue\ (x\ ::\ xs)\ ys\ (\lambda\ ()))$ 
286    $work$  :  $Reverse\ xs\ ys \rightarrow Balance\ ([],\ xs)\ (queue\ ys\ []\ (const\ tt))$ 
287
288 data  $Enq$  :  $Q\ A \rightarrow Q\ A \rightarrow Set$  where
289    $enq\ q$  :  $Balance\ (front\ q_0,\ x\ ::\ rear\ q_0)\ q_1 \rightarrow Enq\ q_0\ q_1$ 
290
291 data  $Deq$  :  $Q\ A \rightarrow Q\ A \rightarrow Set$  where
292    $deq\ i$  :  $\forall\ \{i\} \rightarrow Balance\ (fs,\ rs)\ q \rightarrow Deq\ (queue\ (f\ ::\ fs)\ rs\ i)\ q$ 
293
294
295

```

Note that $Balance$ may call the (linear) list reversal function defined in the previous section. The obvious cost functions count the size of these graphs:

```

296  $cost\ enq$  :  $Enq\ q_0\ q_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ 
297  $cost\ deq$  :  $Deq\ q_0\ q_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ 
298  $cost\ balance$  :  $Balance\ (xs,ys)\ q \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ 
299

```

As $balance$ may require reversing the rear list, the worst case time complexity of $balance$ is linear in the length of the rear list:

$$Balance \in O(\lambda n \rightarrow n)$$

As $balance$ has a worst case linear time complexity, so do both enq and deq .

3.1 Sums of costs

The key idea behind an *amortized* analysis is to find an upper bound on the total cost of a *series of operations*. If the expensive operations are sufficiently rare, these should not have a modest effect on the total cost of the series. We will reproduce the amortized analysis of batched queues in Agda.

Our analysis shifts from the cost of a single operation to series of operations. What are valid series? We restrict ourselves to two queue operations, enqueueing and dequeuing:

data $Op (q_0 : Q A) : Q A \rightarrow Set$ *where*

enq-op : $Enq\ q_0\ q_1 \rightarrow Op\ q_0\ q_1$

deq-op : $Deq\ q_0\ q_1 \rightarrow Op\ q_0\ q_1$

The data type $Op\ q_0\ q_1$ is either an *enq* or *deq* operation, taking the old queue q_0 to a new queue q_1 . Even though dequeuing may fail (when the queue is empty), the *graph* of *Deq* only considers the successful case – hence we never have to worry about the possibility of failure. Next, we chain together a list of queue operations, one after the other:

data $Ops (q_0 : Q A) : Q A \rightarrow Set$ *where*

stop : $Ops\ q_0\ q_0$

step : $Op\ q_0\ q_1 \rightarrow Ops\ q_1\ q_2 \rightarrow Ops\ q_0\ q_2$

Note that the types ensure that each subsequent operation acts on the result of the previous one. Again this definition makes use of *dependent types* to ensure that we *only* have to consider valid sequences of queue operations.

The total cost of such a sequence of queue operations is the sum of the cost of the individual operations:

cost-op : $Op\ q_0\ q_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$

cost-op (*enq-op* e) = *cost-enq* e

cost-op (*deq-op* d) = *cost-deq* d

cost-ops : $Ops\ q_0\ q_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$

cost-ops (*step* $op\ ops$) = *cost-op* op + *cost-ops* ops

cost-ops *stop* = *zero*

Our aim is to find an upper bound on the total cost of a series of queue operations. It is not immediately obvious how to do so: any upper bound must predict how often rebalancing occurs and what the cost is of each expensive rebalancing operation.

3.2 Amortized cost

The key idea behind amortized complexity is due to [Tarjan \(1985\)](#), although we closely follow the presentation by [Hoogerwoord \(1992\)](#). Rather than reasoning about the cost of the sum of operations, we define a notion of credit:

credit : $Q A \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$

For now, we leave underspecified what assumptions we make about this credit function. Note that *credit* is a function on queues – not on operations. We define the amortized cost of a single operation as its cost, together with its change in credit:

358 $credit\ q_0 + amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}ops\ (step\ op\ ops)$
 359 $\equiv \langle \text{definition of } amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}ops \rangle$
 360 $credit\ q_0 + (amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}op\ op + amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}ops\ ops)$
 361 $\equiv \langle \text{definition of } amortized\text{-}cost \rangle$
 362 $credit\ q_0 + ((cost\text{-}op\ op + credit\ q_1 \div credit\ q_0) + amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}ops\ ops)$
 363 $\equiv \langle \text{associativity} \rangle$
 364 $(credit\ q_0 + (cost\text{-}op\ op + credit\ q_1 \div credit\ q_0)) + amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}ops\ ops$
 365 $\equiv \langle \text{monus-addition associativity} \rangle$
 366 $(credit\ q_0 + (cost\text{-}op\ op + credit\ q_1) \div credit\ q_0) + amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}ops\ ops$
 367 $\equiv \langle \text{monus-addition cancellation} \rangle$
 368 $(cost\text{-}op\ op + credit\ q_1) + amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}ops\ ops$
 369 $\equiv \langle \text{associativity} \rangle$
 370 $cost\text{-}op\ op + (credit\ q_1 + amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}ops\ ops)$
 371 $\equiv \langle \text{induction hypothesis} \rangle$
 372 $cost\text{-}op\ op + (cost\text{-}ops\ ops + credit\ q_2)$
 373 $\equiv \langle \text{associativity} \rangle$
 374 $(cost\text{-}op\ op + cost\text{-}ops\ ops) + credit\ q_2$
 375 $\equiv \langle \text{definition of } cost\text{-}ops \rangle$
 376 $cost\text{-}ops\ (step\ op\ ops) + credit\ q_2$

Fig. 2. An equational proof relating amortized and worst case cost

387 $amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}op : Op\ q_0\ q_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$
 388 $amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}op\ \{q_0\}\ \{q_1\}\ op = cost\text{-}op\ op + credit\ q_1 \div credit\ q_0$

389 The amortized cost of a series of operations simply computes the sum of amortized costs:

390 $amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}ops : Ops\ q_0\ q_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$
 391 $amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}ops\ stop = zero$
 392 $amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}ops\ (step\ op\ ops) = amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}op\ op + amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}ops\ ops$

393 Why is this definition useful? When we sum the amortized cost, adjacent credits cancel out!
 394 To make this precise, we prove the following equality:

395 $amortized\text{-}property : (ops : Ops\ q_0\ q_1) \rightarrow$
 396 $credit\ q_0 + amortized\text{-}cost\text{-}ops\ ops \equiv cost\text{-}ops\ ops + credit\ q_1$

401 If we choose the credit of our empty queue to be zero, then we know that the *amortized-cost-ops*
 402 gives an upper bound for total cost. The inductive case of the corresponding proof is in
 403 Figure 2, where $op : Op\ q_0\ q_1$ and $ops : Ops\ q_1\ q_2$; the Agda proof terms have been
 404 replaced with a more legible description.
 405

406 This proof does hinge on several lemmas. All costs are positive natural numbers. The
 407 definition of amortized cost uses a ‘monus’ operation, i.e., cut-off subtraction on natural
 408

409 numbers. Reasoning about the monus is rather subtle, as it does not satisfy the familiar
 410 properties of subtraction on integers. The proof requires that monus cancels addition and that
 411 monus and addition are associative:

412

$$413 \quad m+n \dot{-} m \equiv n : \forall m n \rightarrow (m+n) \dot{-} m \equiv n$$

414

415

$$414 \quad + \dot{-} \text{-assoc} : \forall m \rightarrow o \leq n \rightarrow (m+n) \dot{-} o \equiv m + (n \dot{-} o)$$

416

To use the second lemma, we need to ensure the amortized cost both operations is positive:

417

418

$$418 \quad \text{amortized-cost-positive} : (op : Op q_0 q_1) \rightarrow credit q_0 \leq cost-op op + credit q_1$$

419

420

This side condition guarantees that the amortized cost never ‘overspends’. Each operation
 421 uses no more credits than available; credits are never lost.

422

423

423 3.3 Credits and queues

424

425

All that remains to be done, is to choose the notion of credit for our batched queues. Okasaki
 426 (1998) argues that the *length of the rear* queue gives a suitable notion of credit:

427

$$427 \quad credit : Q A \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$$

428

$$428 \quad credit q = length (rear q)$$

429

430

431

How do our queue operations change the credits available? Each enqueue operation takes
 432 constant time, but increases the accumulated credit as it adds an element to the rear. When
 433 rebalancing occurs, typically after a dequeue operation, we use the accumulated credits to
 434 pay for the expensive list reversal.

435

436

Why is amortization important? Instead of reasoning about the entire sequence of operations,
 437 we know that the amortized cost of the series gives an upper bound on the total cost. We
 438 therefore prove an upper bound on the amortized cost of each single operation:

439

$$439 \quad \text{amortized-bound} : (op : Op q_0 q_1) \rightarrow \text{amortized-cost-op } op \leq 3$$

440

441

Why three? Consider an enqueue operation that does not rebalance: 1) it takes a step to enter
 442 the body of *enq*; 2) it calls *balance*; 3) it allocates one new credit as the resulting *rear* list is
 443 longer. It is easy to construct a similar argument for the other queue operations. The most
 444 interesting case is where rebalancing occurs – but by construction, we will have accumulated
 445 enough credits to pay for the expensive reversal operation.

446

447

If we know that a single operation has a constant amortized cost, the overall cost of any
 448 series of operations is bounded accordingly:

449

$$449 \quad \text{amortized-bound-ops} : (ops : Ops q_0 q_1) \rightarrow \text{amortized-cost-ops } ops \leq 3 * |ops|$$

450

451

Using the key *amortized-property* from the figure above, together with the fact that the empty
 452 queue has zero credit, we show that the *total costs* are bounded:

453

454

$$454 \quad \text{amortized-constant} : (ops : Ops empty q) \rightarrow cost-ops ops \leq 3 * |ops|$$

455

456

Hence we conclude that enqueue, dequeue and rebalancing operations are all amortized
 457 constant time operations.

458

459

4 Discussion

460
461 *Further automation.* Many proof assistants, including Rocq and Lean, provide automation for
462 generating a function’s induction principles from its definition (Barthe et al. 2006; Breitner
463 2024; Sozeau 2010; Sozeau and Mangin 2019); generating the corresponding function graph
464 is very similar. In Agda, we could also use the reflection mechanism to generate these
465 definitions automatically (van der Walt and Swierstra 2012). Rather than define cost functions
466 by hand, one could use metaprogramming or generic programming techniques to generate
467 them (Backhouse et al. 1998; Escot and Cockx 2022; Jansson and Jeuring 1997; Ko et al.
468 2022). There is some manual overhead (and room for error) in writing out all these definitions
469 as we have done here – but doing so is instructive at first.
470

471
472
473
474
475 *Related work.* There is a great deal of related work in the intersection of cost analysis,
476 functional languages, and proof assistants. The recent textbook by Nipkow (2025) gives an
477 overview of purely functional data structures and algorithms, together with their implementa-
478 tion, specification and verification using the interactive proof assistant Isabelle. This book not
479 only gives the precise specification and correctness proofs, but also covers the worst case and
480 amortized complexity analysis. Rather than reify the graph of a function explicitly and define
481 the cost functions inductively, the authors use a metaprogram to generate the cost functions
482 from a function definition directly. This paper explores how to use *dependent types* to model
483 function graphs and series of queue operations, a construction that would be harder to model
484 in Isabelle directly.
485

486 In spirit, our work is most closely related to the Bove-Capretta method (2005). Bove
487 and Capretta have shown how to reify a function’s call graph to decouple its termination
488 proof from its definition; any function can be made structurally recursive in this fashion.
489 Yet there are some differences between our approaches. As our analysis of the slow reverse
490 function shows, it is important to have access to *all* auxiliary function calls – such as the
491 calls to `append` – and not just recursive structure of the function definition under inspection.
492 Furthermore, by including the function’s result in the reified data type, we check that the
493 corresponding data type is sound and complete with respect to its function definition. Where
494 both the Bove-Capretta predicates and function graphs can be generated automatically from a
495 function’s definition, our cost analyses do not require modification to the function’s original
496 definition.
497

498 There are several related approaches to incorporating the cost analysis of a function
499 together with its definition in a proof assistant. Danielsson (2008) has shown how to track
500 the necessary evaluation steps for lazy programs in a function’s type signature in Agda.
501 More recently, the work on cost-aware logical frameworks is also accompanied by an Agda
502 implementation (Grodin et al. 2024; Niu et al. 2022). Provided users write their function in
503 these libraries, they provide an accurate upper bound on the function’s cost. There is a trade
504 off here: using the lightweight techniques suggested in this paper, cost analysis is decoupled
505 from a function’s definition and can be performed *post hoc*, just as other forms of verification.
506 Further afield, there are numerous type and effect systems that track a functional program’s
507 cost or resource usage (Hoffmann et al. 2012; Hoffmann and Hofmann 2010; Hoffmann and
508 Jost 2022; Jost et al. 2010; Rajani et al. 2021).
509
510

511 *Further work.* There are plenty of directions for further research. In particular, we have not
 512 considered *higher-order functions* – but as we are working in a *higher-order logic*, I cannot
 513 foresee any problems in doing so.

514 Our amortized analysis relies on defining a credit function that takes the entire queue as its
 515 input, a technique sometimes referred to as the *physicist’s method*. For some data structures,
 516 however, the amortization argument requires associating credits with particular data type
 517 constructors – known as the *banker’s method*. Here *ornaments* (Dagand 2017; McBride 2010)
 518 might help make this argument both precise and generic.

519 In the amortized analysis of batched queues, the expensive rebalancing operations are rare
 520 and do not dominate the overall cost. Unfortunately, not all programs that work with queues
 521 satisfy this pattern of usage. Consider the following (admittedly contrived) example:

```
522  $f : List A \rightarrow List A$   

  523  $f\ ys = let\ q = queue\ [0]\ [1000000, \dots, 2, 1]\ \lambda\ ()\ in$   

  524  $map\ (\lambda\ y \rightarrow \dots\ deq\ q\ \dots)\ ys$ 
```

525 This function constructs a queue, q , that will require more than a million steps for the next
 526 deq operation. In this example, this rebalancing (potentially) happens over and over again as
 527 the map function is executed. The amortized analysis from the previous section hinges on
 528 rebalancing a queue only once – and cannot be used to limit the cost of the function f above.
 529 Here the queue q is said to be used *persistently* rather than *ephemerally*.

530 To address this, Okasaki (1998) gives several efficient implementations of queues and other
 531 data structures that *can* be used persistently. These queues, however, make essential use of lazy
 532 evaluation. The amortized analyses of data structures that rely on lazy evaluation and sharing
 533 are notoriously difficult. Recent work on first-order laziness facilitate reasoning about the
 534 worst case analysis of data structures using a limited number of lazy operations (Lorenzen et al.
 535 2025). While there has been recent work by Lorenzen (2026) on an operational formalization
 536 of amortization arguments in the presence of laziness, there is still further work necessary to
 537 develop a suitable cost model and reasoning principles.

538 *Conclusion.* In a purely functional language, reasoning relies on elementary methods:
 539 functions are defined by structural induction; proofs follow suit. This paper explores how
 540 induction – albeit on the function’s graph rather than its inputs – offers a convenient way to
 541 reason about a function’s computational complexity by defining a suitable cost function. In
 542 this way, functional programs compute both the value – and cost – of everything.

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